

Health and injury monitoring in disabled athletes

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to develop a health complaints registration applicable for disabled athletes during normal training and preparation phases. This new registration questionnaire was called HIMDA and this study pilot-tested HIMDA for validity and feasibility. A total of 12 wheelchair rugby athletes were monitored prospectively over a 10-week period using HIMDA. Sports participation, health complaints (illnesses and injuries), and the consequences of health complaints were self-registered weekly. A total of 17 health problems were registered, including 4 illnesses, 3 acute injuries and 10 overuse injuries. Only in 10 out of 13 reported injury cases the athletes indicated themselves to be injured. Consequently, the HIMDA overestimated the number of health complaints. However, feasibility of the HIMDA for disabled athletes is good. Therefore, the HIMDA is valid and feasible in documenting the patterns of illness and injury in a group of disabled athletes during normal training and preparation phases. However, the definition of an injury should be clarified in disability sports and relevance should be improved.

Keywords Disabled athletes, health complaints registration, HIMDA, validity, feasibility

Introduction

Even though it is known that exercise can improve physical fitness in wheelchair dependent individuals, participation in physical activities and sports also increases an individual's risk for injury. Apart from the regular burden of an injury, in disabled athlete's injuries further limit their – already restricted- daily life (Weiler et al., 2016). As such, it is of special importance to provide preventative measure against injuries in disabled athletes. There is, however little known about the patterns of sports related injury and their consequences in disabled athletes (Weiler et al., 2016). For this reason, a health complaints registration based on the Oslo Trauma Research Center (OSTRC) questionnaire (Clarsen et al., 2014) was developed for disabled athletes (HIMDA). The research question of this study is: 'Is the HIMDA questionnaire valid and feasible in documenting the patterns of illness and injury in a group of disabled athletes during normal training and preparation phases?'

Methods

A 10 week prospective cohort study was performed, including 12 wheelchair rugby athletes. Sports participation, health complaints (illnesses and injuries), and the consequences of health complaints were self-registered weekly through the online HIMDA questionnaire.

Validity

To test the validity of the HIMDA questionnaire the following variables were evaluated weekly: The severity score (sum of the key questions; score 0-100), the time loss (days/week) and the sought medical attention (Yes/No). It was also evaluated whether the athletes identified themselves to be injured or not.

Feasibility

During the last follow-up week, the athlete's received a short evaluation questionnaire providing information on the feasibility of the HIMDA questionnaire. Questions are all on a 5-point Likert Scale and evaluated technical quality, usability, time investment of the athlete and relevance of the questionnaire.

Results

Validity

A total of 13 injuries were reported, with an average severity score of 38.9 out of 100 (95%CI 25.1-52.7; Range: 8-92). But not in all cases the athletes identified themselves to be injured. The players only indicated themselves to be injured in 10 out of 13 cases. The average severity score when players indicated themselves to be injured was 46.5 (95%CI 31.7-61.3; Range: 22-92). The average severity score for the 3 cases in which the athletes did not indicated themselves to be injured was 13.3 (95%CI 8.1-18.5; Range: 8-16). Consequently, there is a difference in severity and burden of the injuries (Figure 1).

Figure 1; Average severity score with 95%CI whether athletes indicated themselves to be injured or not

When only looked at medical attention and time loss injuries, this is also the case (Figure 2). Athletes that indicated themselves to be injured and sought medical attention had an average severity score of 63.6 (95%CI 43.7-83.5; Range 37-92). The athletes that sought medical attention but that did not indicate themselves to be injured had an average severity score of 12.0 (95%CI 4.2-19.8; Range 8.-16). For time loss, the athletes that indicated themselves to be injured had an average severity score of 64.3 (95%CI 27.9-100.0). None of the athletes that did not indicated themselves to be injured, reported time loss.

Figure 2; Differences in severity scores with 95%CI between the athletes that indicated themselves to be injured (green) and the athletes that did not indicate themselves to be injured (red)

Feasibility

The athletes were positive about the technical quality of the HIMDA questionnaire, with an average score of 4.5 (SD:0.7) point and 4.0 (SD:0.9) points. All athletes scored high in regards to the usability of the HIMDA questionnaire with an average score of 4.8 (SD:0.4). They also reported time investment (<3min) and frequency (once a week) of the HIMDA questionnaire to be good, with respectively average scores of 4.6 (SD:0.7) and 4.5 (SD:0.7). With an average score of 3.1 points (SD:0.7) athletes were neutral about the relevance of the study.

Conclusion and discussion

The study showed that the HIMDA is valid and feasible in documenting the patterns of illness and injury in a group of disabled athletes during normal training and preparation phases. However, there is a difference between all reported injuries and the perception of the athletes when being injured. Differences between the groups became clear when medical attention and time loss were analyzed. Consequently, there is a difference in reported severity and burden of the injuries. Therefore, the definition of an (recordable) injury should be clarified in disability sports. Using the preset definition would reduce the number of reported health problems, but would also reduce the subjectivity of the recorded problems.

Concerning the feasibility of the HIMDA among disabled athletes, the evaluation revealed that the athletes were satisfied with the questionnaire. A critical point of the HIMDA questionnaire was its relevance.

References

- Weiler, R., van Mechelen, W., Fuller, C., Verhagen, E., (2016). Sport injuries sustained by athletes with disability: A systematic review. *Sports medicine*, 46(8), 1141-1153
- Clarsen, B., Rønsen, O., Myklbust, G., Flørenes, T.W., Bahr, R., (2014). The Oslo Sports Trauma Research Center questionnaire on health problems: a new approach to prospective monitoring of illness and injury in elite athletes. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 48(9), 754-760